

Buen Vivir and Epistemic Alterity: Narratives of Resistance from Latin America

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Abstract

This article examines the contemporary relevance of the paradigm of *Buen Vivir* (“Good Living”), a concept rooted in the ancestral knowledge of Indigenous Peoples from South America, that envisions well-being through respect for cultural and environmental diversity, as well as through principles of equality, solidarity, and communal life. Emerging as a decolonial alternative to dominant models of development, *Buen Vivir* offers a political and pedagogical stance that challenges the prevailing logics of profit, commodification, and environmental exploitation. By foregrounding ecological balance, cultural plurality, and collective well-being, it provides a critical framework for rethinking the relationship between humans, nature, and society. This paper argues that integrating the principles of *Buen Vivir* into formal education can foster critical consciousness, promote intercultural dialogue, and disrupt patterns of inequality embedded in historical and structural power relations. Education, in this sense, can serve as a vehicle for advancing epistemological diversity and for challenging the homogenizing and colonial legacies that remain pervasive in the region. The paper highlights the potential of *Buen Vivir* and critical pedagogy as complementary frameworks for constructing more inclusive, sustainable, and just societies.

Keywords

Education, Postcolonialism, Epistemicide, South America, Indigenous People

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Introduction

This paper seeks to contribute to discussions on decolonial approaches to knowledge, society, and education, highlighting the relevance of the paradigm of Buen Vivir (“Good Living” or Sumak Kawsay), rooted in the traditional knowledge of Indigenous Peoples of Latin America. Buen Vivir seeks well-being through respect for cultural and environmental diversity, as well as equality and solidarity. Far from being a nostalgic or purely cultural notion, it carries profound political and pedagogical implications, offering a holistic and meaningful approach to social organization, economy, and education. At its core, Buen Vivir advances a vision of collective flourishing grounded in respect for nature and all living beings, in sharp contrast with the prevailing logics of profit, commodification, and environmental destruction that continue to shape dominant development models.

The urgency of this societal shift is underscored by alarming data that reveal the critical state of our planet. Every year, the world loses approximately 10 million hectares of forest, accelerating the destruction of ecosystems and contributing to an unprecedented decline in biodiversity, with nearly one million species currently at risk of extinction. This rapid depletion of natural resources is compounded by the pervasive problem of plastic pollution: an estimated 8 million tons of plastic enter the oceans annually, threatening marine life and destabilizing fragile marine ecosystems (FAO, 2020). At the same time, the health impacts of environmental degradation are equally severe, as air pollution claims an estimated 7 million lives each year, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations in urban and industrialized areas. Water scarcity further illustrates the depth of the crisis, with projections indicating that global population could face serious shortages of freshwater resources (FAO, 2020). Taken together, these figures illustrate the unsustainable trajectory of profit-oriented socioeconomic models that neglect the intrinsic value of nature. The relentless exploitation of natural resources in the name of economic growth is not only degrading ecosystems but also undermining the resilience of the planet. These crises underscore the urgent need for systemic transformations that integrate ecological, social, and ethical considerations.

Indigenous knowledge is central to this reconfiguration, reframing nature not as an exploitable object but as a living entity endowed with rights and capable of legal recognition. Rooted in Indigenous knowledge and practice, Buen Vivir represents a powerful counterpoint to dominant paradigms: it calls for a balance with nature, prioritizes ecological preservation, cultural respect, and collective well-being, and dismantles the notion of a universal path to progress defined by technological advancement and economic growth (Acosta & Abarca, 2018). This perspective calls for cultivating reciprocal, respectful relationships with the environment based on care, responsibility, and exchange rather than domination. In educational contexts, it represents more than a philosophical principle: it is a radical pedagogical orientation that questions the neutrality of knowledge, reclaims marginalized epistemologies, and opens possibilities for developing curricula that respond to global crises while remaining attentive to local cultural realities.

While official educational policies in Latin America continue to fall short of addressing the needs and aspirations of Indigenous Peoples, incorporating their epistemologies into formal education holds the potential to foster critical thinking and challenge the

patterns of inequality embedded in existing power structures. Yet, this knowledge has long been rendered invisible by the hegemony of a Western-centric perspective, which systematically diminishes the epistemic alterity of non-European peoples (Dussel, 2007). Although recent decades have seen a gradual shift from assimilationist models toward more intercultural approaches (Zsögön, 2025), the recognition and validation of Indigenous knowledge remain far from consolidated within the region’s educational institutions. In this context, the paradigm of Buen Vivir and the principles of critical pedagogy emerge as complementary frameworks, both challenging extractivist and productivist assumptions while fostering alternative ways of living, learning, and relating to one another and to nature.

1. Education in times of globalization, uncertainty and environmental degradation

Environmental degradation is only one of the pressing challenges confronting contemporary society. Its impacts intersect with a range of social, economic, and political issues, leading some scholars to argue that we live in an era defined by uncertainty and the anxiety it breeds. Bauman (2004) emphasizes that both anxiety and uncertainty are among the primary byproducts of globalization, with consumers becoming the central assets of a consumer-driven society. Similarly, Sassen (2014) argues that the concept of inequality alone no longer suffices to explain the global dynamics of our time, and introduces the notion of ‘expulsions’ as a critical framework for analyzing the deep-seated pathologies of global capitalism. The -brutal- dynamics that define our era are reflected in the millions living in misery, the impoverishment of the middle classes, the expulsion of millions of farmers in poor countries, destructive mining practices, the countless displaced persons confined to formal and informal refugee camps, and the unemployed, ‘warehoused’ in ghettos and slums (Bauman, 2004). In this context, democracy is the rule of the elite, who, with the support of the commercial community, control the state through the dominance of private society (Chomsky, 2016). Chomsky argues that school becomes a center for indoctrination and obedience, blocking independent thought, and ultimately maintaining the cultural hegemony of capitalism. This approach reinforces power structures and the system of coercion and control, preventing a critical reading of the world. In the same line, Giroux (2020) points out that the goals of education are reduced to the pragmatic requirements of the market, leading to the training of students as submissive workers and passive citizens. Education, as a culturally dominating practice, is restricted to a situation in which the educator, “who knows,” transfers preexisting knowledge to the student, “who does not know” (Freire, 1970). Students are treated as ‘empty vessels’ to be filled with predetermined ideas, often disconnected from the social reality surrounding them, in order to ensure the preservation of the social order.

For education to be genuinely transformative, it must emphasize social responsibility and cultivate in students a perceptive awareness of their cultural and social context. Such an approach fosters the development of active, engaged citizens capable of critically examining established power structures and patterns of inequality. Within this framework, the philosophy of Buen Vivir assumes particular relevance, as it challenges the consumerist

and extractivist imperatives of capitalism, offering instead a holistic doctrine centered on coexistence, ecological harmony, and respect for all living beings. Buen Vivir is embodied in practices such as responsible production, fair trade, ethical consumption, solidarity-based finance, and community knowledge exchange. These initiatives derive their sustainability from locally rooted social and ecological connections (CIDSE, 2016), offering an ethical framework and a vision for truly equitable and humane living conditions.

Recognizing cultural diversity entails acknowledging that knowledge is produced through multiple perspectives on society, life, and transcendence (Santos, 2009). Around the world, numerous initiatives resonate with the principles of Buen Vivir. Importantly, these alternative visions often originate from marginalized communities and compel us to question mainstream, growth-oriented concepts of development (Acosta & Abarca, 2018). Many understandings of Buen Vivir have existed for centuries, but are only now being drawn into the debate around development (Gudynas, 2011). To fully grasp the philosophical and epistemological foundations of Buen Vivir, it is essential to situate it within the Latin American pre-colonial context, before Indigenous knowledge was systematically subordinated and marginalized during centuries of conquest and colonization.

2. Epistemicide as the legacy of colonialism

Latin America is characterized by its cultural diversity, vast natural wealth, yet it continues to face persistent structural challenges, particularly poverty and inequality. According to the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC, 2023), approximately 29% of the population lived in poverty in 2022, with rural areas and Indigenous communities disproportionately affected. Indigenous Peoples are more than twice as likely to live in poverty compared to non-Indigenous populations. Inequality in the region remains among the highest globally, with the wealthiest 10% controlling around 30% of total income while the poorest 20% receive only 6% (UNESCO, 2020). These disparities reflect enduring legacies of colonialism and structural exclusion, which continue to shape socio-economic realities across the region. The COVID-19 pandemic has further deepened these vulnerabilities, exacerbating social gaps and disproportionately affecting women, youth, and historically marginalized populations (ECLAC, 2021). At the same time, Latin America is home to abundant natural resources, including vast rainforests, fertile agricultural lands, and significant mineral reserves of copper, silver, and lithium. The Amazon rainforest, primarily located in Brazil, represents the world's largest tropical rainforest and a critical global ecological asset. Indigenous Peoples number an estimated 45 million, belonging to more than 800 ethnic groups with extensive demographic, social, territorial, and political diversity, ranging from communities in voluntary isolation to those living in major urban centers (ECLAC, 2014). Countries such as Mexico, Peru, Guatemala, and Bolivia host the largest Indigenous populations, both in absolute and proportional terms, together comprising over 80% of the total Indigenous population (34.4 million). In contrast, countries including El Salvador, Brazil, Paraguay, Argentina, Uruguay, Costa Rica, and Venezuela exhibit smaller proportions of Indigenous peoples, with El Salvador and Costa Rica having the smallest populations in absolute terms, at 14,865 and 104,143 individuals respectively (World Bank, 2015).

The structural inequalities that characterize Latin America today can be traced back to the colonial period, when European powers established extractive economic systems that consolidated patterns of exclusion and stratification (Bértola & Williamson, 2017). During this time, institutions were designed to serve the interests of the colonizers, reinforcing hierarchies that privileged European elites while marginalizing Indigenous and Afro-descendant populations. Education played a central role in this process: rather than fostering inclusive knowledge or critical capacity, it was structured to consolidate colonial domination, instill discipline, and secure subordination to ruling elites (Tedesco, 2012; UNESCO, 2020). Although the wars of independence in the 19th century marked a formal break with colonial rule, they did not dismantle the deeply embedded social and economic asymmetries that persist into the present.

Anibal Quijano (2014) mentions that, since the 18th century, in the centers of the global power system, a mode of producing knowledge was developed and formalized that addressed the cognitive needs of capitalism: measurement, quantification, and the externalization (objectification) of the ‘knowable’ with respect to the ‘knower’. Quijano emphasizes that this mode of knowledge was called ‘rational’ due to its Eurocentric nature and origin; it was imposed and accepted throughout the capitalist world as the only valid rationality and as an emblem of modernity. The main lines of this cognitive perspective have been maintained throughout the duration of the global power of colonial and modern capitalism, and are visible in a subtle racism that considers non-European cultures inferior.

Eurocentric knowledge was labelled as the sole valid rationality within the capitalist world (Quijano, 2014). This idea is consistent with the claim of universality of the knowledge produced by the “Global North”, which determines what is considered valid knowledge at each historical moment. This epistemological interference was made possible by the force of the political, economic, and military intervention of modern colonialism and capitalism. An intervention that, according to Boaventura de Sousa Santos, discredited and even suppressed all social practices of knowledge that ran counter to the interests it served. For Santos, this “epistemicide” was the pretext for the colonizing mission that sought to homogenize the world and resulted in the loss of epistemological, cultural, and political diversity (Santos, 2014). This enduring form of symbolic violence has, for centuries, undermined the ontological and epistemological richness of non-Western peoples, resulting in profound cultural and linguistic erasures and serving as both a consequence and continuation of the multiple genocides that claimed millions of lives across the Global South in the indefensible pursuit of Indigenous lands and their resources (Monzó, 2017:9).

Ethnocide and ecocide are frequently invoked as legal foundations for Indigenous resistance to recurring, institutionalized, and often state-sanctioned violence, as Indigenous Peoples continue to face profound challenges in sustaining their existence and preserving non-Western cultures (Resende et al, 2025).

The physical and symbolic violence endured by Indigenous populations was historically followed by state-led efforts to assimilate them into the dominant culture. Although contemporary discourses on interculturality in education aspire to promote recognition and inclusivity, such aspirations remain largely rhetorical. In practice, the knowledge systems of Indigenous Peoples continue to be relegated to a subordinate position, or excluded

altogether, within the school curricula of the region (Tedesco, 2012). Recognizing cultural diversity means acknowledging that knowledge takes many forms. However, the region's educational systems have adopted a European perspective in linguistic, religious, and historical domains, actively resisting the integration of non-European traditions and populations, a problem that persists to this day (UNESCO, 2020:55). In Brazil, for instance, the state conceived "Indigenous" as a transitory social category, until Indigenous Peoples were assimilated into other officially recognized non-Indigenous racial categories (Resende et al, 2025).

In the 19th and 20th centuries, Latin American countries developed curricula aimed at consolidating a national identity for their emerging nations, primarily grounded in the dominant Western colonial heritage (Tedesco, 2012). Curricular priorities focused on Spanish, Catholicism, and European history and geography, with little regard for local traditions. This emphasis introduced a significant bias, giving Western European knowledge greater legitimacy and visibility, while marginalizing the histories, languages, and cultural contributions of Afro-descendant and Indigenous Peoples. These patterns of exclusion continue to influence educational content and reinforce inequities in recognition and representation. The cultural, ideological, and political dominance of one culture over another directly shaped this clearly directional educational project, producing a system that disregarded the cognitive organization and knowledge-construction mechanisms of diverse peoples and cultures. Built upon this foundation, a uniform curriculum, both Spanish-speaking and Christianizing, was systematically imposed across the region, enforcing a form of education that not only prioritized European perspectives but also required communities to "unlearn" their own cultural knowledge and, in many cases, abandon their mother tongues. Together, these processes created an enduring framework of homogenizing education, (re)producing cognitive, cultural, and symbolic impoverishment (Comboni Salinas & Juárez Núñez, 2020). This is why, for Indigenous students, formal education is often perceived as irrelevant. They frequently recognize that the education provided by the state promotes individualism and a competitive atmosphere rather than fostering communal ways of life and cooperation. In many cases, these students return to their communities having acquired knowledge and skills from formal schooling that are disconnected from (or even inappropriate for) their cultural and practical needs (UN, 2010:5). In this sense, some government initiatives aim to incorporate Indigenous knowledge into mainstream schools as a way of recognizing and valuing this knowledge. UNESCO (2020) highlights several such initiatives, including Colombia's *Proyecto Educativo Comunitario* (Community Educational Project), which integrates Indigenous community perspectives within the framework of national educational guidelines. Another initiative focuses on the Mokaná Indigenous group, which has incorporated curriculum content on Indigenous legislation, myths and oral history, agricultural and community production practices. Schooling in this context respects the Mokaná calendar. Other countries in Latin America and the Caribbean have made significant progress in incorporating bilingualism into the education system, particularly for Indigenous Peoples. Bolivia's Plurinational Institute for the Study of Languages and Cultures (IPELC) and its 28 Language and Culture Institutes design policies and strategic actions to promote Indigenous languages and cultures (Corbetta et al., 2018). These institutes have recovered and published 23 alphabets of Indigenous Peoples and Nations (Bolivian Ministry of Education, 2017). The approach underlying Intercultural Bilingual Education promotes social and political

transformation, as it fosters appreciation and appropriation of the cultural and symbolic legacies of the indigenous population. This reaffirmation of indigenous languages also provides a window into another worldview and cosmogony (Abarca Cariman, 2015).

3. Buen Vivir and the revalorization of Indigenous Epistemologies

For Indigenous Peoples in Ecuador and Bolivia, *Sumak Kawsay*, or “good living,” represents a life of fullness, centered on harmony, solidarity, and reciprocity. Beyond being a historical and political project, it embodies traditional knowledge about living in harmony and balance, with the earth, the cosmos, life, and history, and in equilibrium with all existence. These alternative societal constructs are expressed through concepts such as *Buen Vivir* (Spanish), *Sumak Kawsay* (Kichwa), and *Suma Qamaña* (Aymara), and are echoed among other Indigenous groups, including the Mapuche in Chile and Argentina, the Guaraní in Paraguay, Brazil, Argentina, and Bolivia, and the Kuna in Panama and Colombia. Similar worldviews are also found in Mayan traditions in Guatemala and among the Indigenous populations of Chiapas, Mexico (Acosta & Abarca, 2018).

As Gudynas (2011) points out, the richness of the term is difficult to translate into English: it includes the classical ideas of quality of life, but with the specific idea that well-being is only possible within a community, understood in an expanded sense, to include Nature. Buen Vivir therefore embraces the broad notion of well-being and cohabitation with others and Nature (Gudynas, 2011:441). Buen Vivir is a way of life that seeks to ensure happiness and the preservation of cultural and environmental diversity, emphasizing harmony, equality, equity, and solidarity. While there is no single definition of Buen Vivir, it is often associated with collective well-being and is emerging through diverse perspectives and social actors across South America. Fundamentally, Buen Vivir represents a decolonial stance. It calls for a new ethical framework that balances quality of life, the democratization of the state, and a commitment to biocentric principles. Drawing on the wealth of the region’s Indigenous cultures, it has also emerged as a lived practice resisting commodification and promoting alternative ways of organizing life (Gudynas, 2009). Buen Vivir emphasizes collective well-being, cultural and environmental diversity, and the pursuit of equality and equity, standing in contrast to individualistic and extractivist models of development. In fact, the concept of development does not exist in many indigenous systems of knowledge. They do not espouse a linear vision of life, such as the path leading from underdevelopment to development (Acosta & Abarca, 2018). In the 1990s, this debate led to the launch of the Human Development Index, inspired by Amartya Sen’s (1999) innovative proposal to understand development not merely as an increase in economic satisfiers, but as a process of expanding the real freedoms that individuals enjoy.

By the early 2000s, it was clear that compensatory fixes could not address the harms of conventional development, making the classical model untenable. Although Buen Vivir emerged largely independently from post-development debates, it shares strong affinities with them, as both entail a radical deconstruction of the cultural foundations of development (Gudynas, 2011). A critical perspective on development is not limited to Latin America; it is also present in Europe. In this context, the concept of Buen Vivir

is beginning to gain traction as part of a broader dialogue that questions conventional development models, even though many critiques remain anchored in the logic of economic growth. Nevertheless, emerging European initiatives linked to *Buen Vivir* reflect a growing interest in revitalizing local communities and transforming key sectors such as food systems, education, social care, transportation, energy production, and, more recently, public health in response to the COVID-19 crisis (Hernández & Laats, 2020).

The proposal of *Buen Vivir* is based on the ethics and morals of ancestral indigenous culture, from which arises the idea of a sacred nature, capable of withdrawing the sustenance that communities require if it is treated inappropriately (Torres-Solis & Ramírez-Valverde, 2019). Within this paradigm, education plays a central role: the right to education is considered an essential component of *Buen Vivir*, as it enables the realization of human potential while guaranteeing equal opportunities for all. In line with UNESCO's (2021) view of knowledge and education as common goods that embody humanity's diverse ways of knowing, living, and being, and demands the valorization of marginalized cultures and epistemologies. Critical pedagogy, grounded in the work of Paulo Freire (1970) emphasizes the formation of critical and reflective individuals who are socially responsible and culturally aware. Freire, together with Fanon, provide guidelines for constructing pedagogies as practices of learning, unlearning, and relearning. They shift the focus of pedagogy away from traditional educational discourses, demonstrating through their thinking and practice how social struggles themselves can also serve as pedagogical spaces (Walsh, 2013). In this context, decolonial pedagogy emerges as a form of praxis based on a proactive, insurgent approach to education, one that goes beyond critique to actively create and construct new social, political, cultural, and cognitive conditions. It develops pedagogical concepts and visions that extend beyond mere teaching and knowledge transmission, framing pedagogy itself as a form of cultural politics (Comboni Salinas & Juárez Núñez, 2020). Interculturality, conceived from this perspective, represents the construction of a new epistemological space that positions marginalized knowledges in critical and often tense dialogue with Western knowledge, fostering a more equitable and reflective relationship between them (Walsh, 2007). Complementing this, the *Buen Vivir* paradigm, seeks collective well-being through respect for cultural and environmental diversity, equality, and solidarity. Far from being merely philosophical, *Buen Vivir* carries profound political and pedagogical implications, offering a holistic approach to education and life that is grounded in reciprocity with nature and respect for all living beings.

The Kichwa expression *sumak kawsay* and its Aymara counterpart *suma qamañac* (both translated as "living well") entered Latin American political discourse at the beginning of the 21st century. Early articulations of *Buen Vivir* arose as a response to conventional development strategies, which were increasingly questioned for their adverse social and environmental consequences, as well as their contested economic outcomes. Numerous critiques emphasized the limitations and harmful effects of development projects promoted by governments and multilateral development banks across Latin America in recent decades (Gudynas, 2011). Their rise was shaped by several converging factors: the discrediting of nation-states, which had lost much of their capacity to regulate economies and respond to social demands; the erosion of the dominant concept of development, increasingly seen as a symptom of modernity's crisis; and the emergence of social movements that positioned themselves as political actors resisting neoliberalism and global colonialism (Torres-Solis & Ramírez-Valverde, 2019).

The notion of *Buen Vivir* began to gain traction in regional and global debates on sustainability when heads of state, government leaders, and high-level representatives from around the world convened in Rio de Janeiro for the United Nations Rio+20 Summit in 2012. One of the key outcomes of this meeting was the document *The Future We Want*, which set out a vision for an economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable future for the planet and for both present and future generations. However, the initiative was met with skepticism and resistance from civil society organizations, which criticized its reliance on conventional development paradigms. In response, the alternative People’s Summit at Rio+20 launched the declaration *Another Future is Possible*, articulating a vision for sustainability rooted in social justice and ecological responsibility (RIO+20 Portal, 2025). This counter-discourse drew inspiration from transformative projects already reshaping South America since the mid-2000s, particularly the paradigm of *Buen Vivir*, which had been formally incorporated into international debates two years earlier during the People’s Climate Summit in Cochabamba, Bolivia (2010).

Buen Vivir has also gained recognition in the normative legal framework of South America. *Sumak Kawsay* is a central principle in the Constitution of Ecuador, which positions Mother Nature, or Pachamama, as a subject of rights. Article 71 recognizes that “Nature or Pachamama, where life is reproduced or realized, has the right to have its existence, maintenance, and regeneration of its vital cycles, structure, functions, and evolutionary processes fully respected.” From the perspective of Indigenous philosophy or worldview, Pachamama is a living being. In this sense, nature and the concept of *Buen Vivir* are part of ancient visions rooted in integral harmony (Walsh, 2012). Meanwhile, Article 72 of the Constitution of Ecuador establishes that “Nature has the right to restoration. This restoration shall be independent of the obligation of the State and natural or legal persons to compensate individuals and collectives who depend on the affected natural systems” (Constitution of Ecuador). In the Ecuadorian Constitution, the Good Life is established in relation to several key areas: water and food; culture and science; education; habitat and housing; health and work; the rights of communities, peoples, and nationalities; and the rights of nature; the economy; and social participation (Cujabante Villamil, 2014). In Bolivia, although they do not have constitutional status, Law No. 071 (from 2010) promulgates the rights of Mother Earth and establishes, in Article 3, that “Mother Earth is the dynamic living system formed by the indivisible community of all life systems and living beings, interrelated, interdependent, and complementary, sharing a common destiny. Mother Earth is considered sacred, according to the worldviews of Indigenous, Native, and peasant nations and peoples.” The two constitutions approach *Buen Vivir* differently. Bolivia frames it as an ethical principle that values cultural diversity but does not recognize it as a right, while Ecuador adopts a stronger formulation by conceiving it as a plural set of rights. Despite these differences, *Buen Vivir* is united by core ideas: it serves as a platform for critical perspectives on development, redefines nature as a subject rather than an object, and challenges Eurocentric paradigms by advancing alternatives to conventional development (Gudynas, 2011). This idea seeks to counter the destructive consequences of what has been termed the “civilization of waste.” Yet, despite notable advances in political discourse and legal recognition, the vision of *Buen Vivir* remains only partially realized. Its principles continue to encounter resistance within societies that not only perpetuate the marginalization of Indigenous Peoples but also remain firmly anchored in Western ideals of material accumulation, and consumerist lifestyles (Torres-Solis & Ramírez-Valverde, 2019). Moreover, it has been suggested that the enduring

memories of injustices committed against Indigenous Peoples -both historically and in the present- played a role in the rise of multicultural agendas across the region. In many cases, pervasive feelings of guilt contributed to the adoption of policies of symbolic recognition, which, while politically expedient and cost-effective, often fell short of producing substantive structural change (Aguilar Rivera, 2014: 32).

Conclusion

*The past, our stories local and global, the present,
our communities, cultures, languages and social practices
all may be spaces of marginalization, but they have also become
spaces of resistance and hope (Smith, 1999)*

In a world increasingly defined by violent conflicts, systemic exploitation, discrimination, class divisions, and the relentless forces of globalization, knowledge cannot be regarded as neutral or detached from the power structures that shape it. Education, therefore, must move beyond reproducing dominant paradigms and instead form students as active, critically engaged citizens, committed to transforming unjust realities. Both critical pedagogy and Buen Vivir offer complementary tools for cultivating this awareness, encouraging learners to engage with cultural contexts and their own identities in ways that are community-centered, ecologically balanced, and culturally sensitive. Together, they present a powerful alternative to neoliberal models of education that prioritize competitiveness, individualism, and market-driven logics over solidarity, justice, and collective well-being. In this sense, Buen Vivir and education are mutually reinforcing, offering a framework that integrates inclusion, reciprocity, and the recognition of diverse epistemologies as key to human flourishing. By integrating these perspectives, we can foster a more inclusive and equitable approach to education and societal development. The multiple environmental crises we face today reveal the unsustainable trajectory of a profit-driven system that reduces nature to a resource for extraction and consumption, overlooking its intrinsic value. Against this backdrop, the paradigm of Buen Vivir offers a profound critique and an alternative framework. Rather than reinforcing growth-oriented logics of development, it advances an ethic of balance with nature, grounded in ecological preservation, cultural respect, and the collective well-being of communities. As such, Buen Vivir not only challenges dominant paradigms but also provides an educational horizon that emphasizes interconnectedness, ecological responsibility, and social justice; dimensions that are urgently required in rethinking sustainability and resilience.

The critical challenge lies in designing and implementing policies that genuinely defend nature, even when doing so conflicts with immediate economic and political interests. In the context of escalating environmental degradation and unprecedented strain on Earth's resilience, integrating alternative epistemologies is an urgent task. Embedding Indigenous cosmovision into educational curricula represents a promising pathway, promoting genuine intercultural exchange, valorizing epistemological diversity, and positioning education as a central mechanism for advancing cultural pluralism, challenging homogenizing colonial traditions, and fostering more sustainable and equitable futures.

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